

Electrical Conductivity and Thermoelectric Power of SO₂ Clathrate of Hydroquinone

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Electrical conductivity and thermoelectric power of pellets of SO₂ clathrate of hydroquinone were measured in the temperature range of 25 to 80°. The activation energy of conduction, 0.77 eV is related to half of the energy gap. The energy gap estimated from the data of thermoelectric power is 1.53 eV. The sign of the majority charge carrier is reported to be negative. Other semiconducting parameters like mobility- μ mean free path l - and relaxation time τ show variable values: (μ 4.0-0.1 cm²/volt sec, l -0.50 Å and τ 2 × 10⁻⁸ × 10⁻¹⁰ sec).

ELECTRICAL phenomena associated with organic compounds has been the interest of many investigators engaged in materials research. The name organic compound in the present paper has been confined to those organic solids which exhibit semiconductivity. Basically, three types of organic compounds are considered for their semiconducting behaviour; (i) Compounds involving delocalised electrons (π electrons) e.g. condensed polycyclic aromatic compounds, (naphthalene, anthracene, pthalocyanines and some dyestuffs). (ii) Compounds involving unpaired electrons or free radicals. (iii) Polymer or intermolecular addition compounds i.e. complexes formed between aromatic hydrocarbons and alkali metals, between aromatic compounds and halogen, halogenated quinones and so on.

Electrical conduction of hundreds of organic solids has been investigated by several workers and the results have been interpreted primarily with the help of theories originally devised on the basis of the behaviour of elemental inorganic semiconductors such as Si and Ge. The lacking in the understanding of the operating intermolecular forces and their interactions in the molecular solids are primarily responsible for the absence of a comprehensive theory of conduction of organic solids. However, there are three models which are usually accepted for interpreting the conduction behaviour in these molecular solids. These three are based on the energy band model^{1, 2, 3}, the tunneling model^{4, 5} and the model of exciton migration⁶. The experimentally observed activation energy of conduction in molecular solid, is thus interpreted whichever of three is best applicable to experimental results.

In the above paragraph it has been referred only the organic semiconducting materials whose resistivity is fairly high of the order of 10¹² ohm cm or so. B. Rosenberg^{7, 8} however, reported that in the moist sample of protein the resistivity decreases by several orders of magnitude and he has suggested two regions

namely, electronic and ionic depending upon the moles of water adsorbed by the compound. Similar behaviour observed accidentally in this work on SO₂ clathrate of hydroquinone aroused the interest to investigate the electronic region in detail. In the present work attempt has been made to measure electrical conductivity and thermoelectric power on moist pellet of SO₂ clathrate of hydroquinone. Moist sample was also preferred because the conductivity of the dry material was exceedingly low to be measured by the present apparatus.

Materials and Methods

A concentrated solution of hydroquinone in distilled water was saturated with SO₂ gas at 25° and thereby a yellow granular solid precipitated out. The hydroquinone used here was A.R. grade and sublimed twice. The SO₂ gas was prepared from Cu/- conc. H₂SO₄ reaction and dried by passing the gas through traps containing conc. H₂SO₄ and anhydrous calcium chloride. The yellow solid washed with acetone (A. R.) and ethyl alcohol, was vacuum filtered, dried and stored in a desiccator for further use. The pellets of the clathrate were prepared from finely ground samples by a pressing machine, the pressure being of 2000 psi for two minutes. The area of the pellet was 1 cm² and the thickness varied from 1 to 5 mm. Thicker pellets were needed for thormoelectric power measurements.

A. C. conductivity measurements were made with the help of a conductance bridge Toshniwal type model No CLO1.01 operating at 220 volts A. C. input and 50 cps. This bridge can measure conductivity in this range of 10⁻¹ to 10⁻⁷ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ on the full scale, the null point being determined by the magic eye built within the instrument. The sample was sandwiched between two bright aluminium circular electrodes each, electrode being attached with a copper constantan thermocouple.

The contact between sample and the electrodes was insured by an external spring. The assembly was suspen-

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ded in an electrical furnace to measure the conductivity at different temperatures. The temperatures of the furnace was controlled by regulating the power from the main through a variac. Moles of water was maintained and determined by weighing the total electrode assembly with pellet at each reading.

For thermoelectric power thermal e.m.f. ΔV was measured by a D. C. microvoltmeter Philips model 6020 and with the electrode assembly used for conductivity measurements. The temperature gradient, ΔT was maintained by a small heater attached with one of the electrodes. Several readings were taken at a fixed temperature by varying the temperature gradient and the slope (dv/dt) was taken as the thermoelectric power. A typical plot of $\Delta V/\Delta T$ is shown in the Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Data showing the variation of Thermal E. M. F. with temperature gradient.

Fig. 2. Conductivity data moist pallet of SO_2 Clathrate of hydroquinone.

Results and Discussion

Electrical conductivity measurements on moist pellets of SO_2 clathrate of hydroquinone were made in the temperature range of 25° to 80° . Some difficulty was experienced in measuring conductivity towards lower temperature. However, the results of three different samples were fairly reproducible, the limits of error being about 5 percent. The Arrhenius plot of conductivity data has been shown in Fig. 2 and the plot gives a reasonable straight line with an activation energy of 0.77 eV. The value of specific conductivity at 25° and 80° are $3.98 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $5.63 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

Thermoelectric power or Seebeck coefficient θ was also measured in the same temperature range as that of conductivity. The results of such measurements are shown in Fig. 3 in which θ (mv/deg) is plotted against $T^\circ\text{K}$. From $(\theta-T)$ curve it appears that θ varies inversely

Fig. 3. Thermoelectric power data of SO_2 Clathrate of hydroquinone.

with temperature. The cold end indicated the negative sign, thus the majority of the current carrier seems to be electron. Thermoelectric power θ and fermi energy E_0 are related by simple expressions⁹ for positive holes (1) and electrons (2) respectively.

$$\theta eT = E_0 - E_v + 2kT \quad (1)$$

$$-\theta eT = E_0 - E_c + 2kT \quad (2)$$

where E_v and E_c are the energy at the top of valence band and at the bottom of conduction band respectively, e and k have the usual meaning. These results were used to calculate the parameters like conc. of charge carriers n , the mobility μ , mean free path l , and relaxation time τ using the following expressions (3) and (4).

$$n = N_c \exp\left(\frac{E_c - E_0}{kT}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $n = \text{conc. of electrons/cm}^3$

$$N_c = 2 \left(\frac{2\pi m^* kT}{h^2}\right)^{3/2}$$

m^* = Effective mass of electron

h = Planck's constant

and
$$\mu = \frac{\sigma}{n^0}, \quad (4)$$

where σ = Specific conductivity ($\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)

μ = mobility ($\text{cm}^2/\text{volt. sec.}$)

Therefore
$$l = 4.12 \times 10^{-10} \mu T^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ (cm)} \quad (5)$$

Since $\mu = \frac{4}{3} (e) (2\pi m^* kT)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \text{ e.s.u.}$

and if $m^* = m$ (electronic mass)

then
$$\mu = 2.43 \times 10^9 T^{-\frac{1}{2}} \text{ (cm}^2/\text{volt sec.)}$$

$\therefore l = 4.12 \times 10^{-10} \mu T^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ (cm)}$

and
$$\tau = \frac{m^* \mu}{e} \text{ (sec)} \quad (6)$$

These parameters together with specific conductance $\sigma_{\delta p}$ and θ have been tabulated in table 1. In this calculation the effective mass of the charge carrier (electron) is taken to be equal to that of electronic mass and the model assumes the band model. From the table 1 it appears that conc. of charge carriers increases with rise in temperature. The plot of $\log_{10} n$ vs $\frac{10^3}{T(^{\circ}K)}$ gives a reasonably good straight line, (see Fig. 4) with a slope of 1.54 eV. The mobility on the other hand decreases exponentially with increasing temperature as shown in Fig. 5. The exponential decrease of μ is more apparent from the Fig. 6 where $\log \mu$ vs T plot is linear.

Fig. 4. Arrhenius plot of majority charge carrier concentration.

Fig. 5. Data showing the mobility variation with temperature.

Fig. 6. Data showing the linear dependence of mobility with temperature.

It has been pointed out in the introduction that there are three models which are generally used for interpreting the conduction behaviour of organic solids. These are band model, tunneling model and excitation model. It seems that the band model is most appropriate and therefore, the results were analysed by using the typical behaviour of a semiconductor.

The behaviour of a typical semiconductor is represented by the following empirical relation (7).

$$\rho = \rho_0 \exp (e/kT) \quad (7)$$

where ρ = Electrical resistivity

ρ_0 = Specific resistivity

e = Activation energy of conduction process

TABLE 1—ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY AND THERMOELECTRIC POWER DATA OF SO₂ CLATHRATE OF HYDROQUINONE

T (°K)	Log ₁₀ σ sp (ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Thermo- electric Power θ (mv/deg)	(E _c - E ₀)* eV	Charge carrier (electron) conc. (cm ⁻³)	Mobility (cm ² /volt sec.)	Mean free path (cm)	Rel. xation time (sec.)
298	-7.40						
311	-6.76	1.34	0.49	2.37 × 10 ¹¹	4.55	4.48 × 10 ⁻⁹	2.58 × 10 ⁻⁸
316	-6.54	1.33	0.47	7.15 × 10 ¹¹	2.52	4.31 × 10 ⁻⁹	1.43 × 10 ⁻⁸
322	-6.30	1.27	0.46	1.61 × 10 ¹²	1.93	4.95 × 10 ⁻⁹	1.10 × 10 ⁻⁸
327	-6.12	1.26	0.44	4.27 × 10 ¹²	1.13	4.72 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.64 × 10 ⁻⁸
333	-5.91	1.19	0.41	1.47 × 10 ¹³	0.54	4.16 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.30 × 10 ⁻⁸
340	-5.69	1.13	0.39	4.46 × 10 ¹³	0.26	3.60 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.15 × 10 ⁻⁸
345	-5.51	1.12	0.38	7.26 × 10 ¹³	0.26	4.50 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.15 × 10 ⁻⁸
354	-5.21	1.12	0.35	3.62 × 10 ¹⁴	0.10	4.07 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.06 × 10 ⁻⁸

* E₀ = Energy at the bottom of conduction band .

E₀⁻ = Fermi energy

The activation energy in the above expression is related to the energy of formation of the current carriers. Thus if the conduction is related to the mobile charge carriers which are free from a band or donor state, and excited to an upper level, the upper level being separated from the lower level by an energy ϵ , the number of charge carriers should be proportional to $e^{-\epsilon/2kT}$ provided there are no donor vacant states initially^{10,11}. If the mobility or mean free path of the charge carriers is presumed to depend slowly on temperature, the following relations hold good for the resistivity

$$\rho = \rho_0 \exp(-\epsilon/2kT) \quad (8)$$

and consequently the specific conductivity σ is given by the equation (9)

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-\epsilon/2kT) \quad (9)$$

Now looking at the results of conduction process in the present sample of SO₂ clathrate of hydroquinone, the activation energy is about 0.77 eV. According to equation (9) this activation energy represents $\epsilon/2$ and therefore the expected value of the band gap amounts to 1.54 eV. The energy gap determined from the plot $\log n$ vs $1/T$ (see Fig 4) is 1.53 eV and is in good agreement with the value 1.54 eV estimated from conductivity measurement. Such an excellent agreement from of the conductivity results with that of thermoelectric power data adds to the confidence in arriving at the conclusion that band model is justified in the present system. The electrons are thermally excited from the valence band to the top of conduction band and the activation energy of conductivity represents the half of the forbidden gap. This means that the material is behaving as an intrinsic semiconductor. However, it is not clearly understood whether the π electrons (π_1 , π_2 and π_3) of the benzene ring are excited to bands of antibonding orbitals (π_4^* , π_5^* and π_6^*) conduction band, of carbon atoms or to the bands of antibonding orbitals of sulphur in sulphur dioxide molecules. In order to

clarify whether SO₂ molecule is involved in the conduction process the work on another clathrate of hydroquinone is in progress.

Other parameters like the mobility, the mean free path and relaxation time have been tabulated in table 1. The temperature dependence of mobility indicates that some sort of scattering type behaviour of the charge carriers is most probable. But we do not understand at this stage clearly whether the lattice scattering or impurity scattering is operating in this case. However, it is speculated that impurity scattering is more probable because the sample under investigation is polycrystalline. The values of mobility ranges from about 4.5 cm²/volt sec. to about 0.10 cm²/volt sec. Such values of mobility, though low for electrons, could be attributed to the polycrystalline nature of the sample. The relaxation time and the mean free path are of the order of 10⁻⁸ sec. and 10⁻¹ Å respectively. The value of mean free path is not in accordance with the band model because this should have been of the order of several lattice parameter if the band model is valid. The smaller value of mean free path is probably due to the fact that the velocity of the electron in the band is not appropriately taken. LeBlanc¹² has shown that taking the appropriate velocity of electrons and holes in these bands with experimentally observed mobilities yielded scattering parameters indicating that the carriers travel several lattice parameters before being scattered. At present we do not have the Hall Effect data therefore, further clarification is waited until our Hall mobility is available.

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